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Impact of the flow-field distribution channel cross-section geometry on PEM fuel cell performance: Stamped vs. milled channel

Miroslav Hala^a, Roman Kodým^a, Martin Prokop^a, Martin Paidar^a, Katie McCay^b, Luca Ansaloni^c, Karel Bouzek^{a,*}

^a Department of Inorganic Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Technická 5, 16628, Prague 6, Czech Republic

^b Department of Sustainable Energy Technology, SINTEF AS, Sem Sælands vei 12, 7034 Trondheim, Norway

^c Department of Sustainable Energy Technology, SINTEF AS, Forskningsveien 1, 0373 Oslo, Norway

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ABSTRACT

Polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells (PEM FCs) represent an essential part of the emerging hydrogen economy. Metallic bipolar plates (BPs) allow high speed and capacity production using established industrial technologies, like mechanical stamping. Stamping, however, leads to different cross-sectional shapes of flow-field (FF) channels as compared to milled or compression-moulded bipolar plates. The impact of these changes on the resulting fuel cell performance is not yet fully understood. This study employs an experimentally validated three-dimensional, isothermal, steady-state, continuum-mechanics based mathematical model to gain a deeper insight into this issue and to identify optimal stamped BP channel cross-sectional shapes for parallel and serpentine FF. The uniformity of the local distribution of the physico-chemical quantities and the resulting load curves are analysed. The results obtained confirm that stamped BPs with channels of the trapezoidal cross-section are a viable alternative to the traditional milled or moulded BPs with channels of the rectangular cross-section. The observed differences in performance of FC with stamped and milled channels can be mitigated by optimization of the channel cross-section geometry parameters. As an optimal rib width 0.4 mm and an optimal channel ground width 1 mm for milled and 0.2 mm for stamped BPs are suggested.

1. Introduction

Polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells are a crucial part of the emerging hydrogen economy [1]. However, the manufacturability and costs of PEM FC components have hindered their widespread commercialization. Specifically, bipolar plates constitute 20–30 % of the total PEM FC stack cost [2]. Metallic BPs formed by stamping offer a promising cost-effective and easily manufacturable alternative to graphite and composite materials [3–5]. During forming, however, metallic plates are subjected to high mechanical stresses and this limits the geometry of the flow field and individual channels in the final plates [6–8]. Altogether, this leads to different flow-field channel cross-section shapes and channel configurations, as compared to the rectangular ones produced by milling or moulding. High aspect ratios and sharp edges of the BP structures comparable to graphite-based BPs produced by machine milling or pressure moulding cannot be achieved [7]. The impact of these changes on the resulting PEM FC performance is not yet fully

understood.

Both the flow-field design and the cross-section geometries of the channels need to be considered to ensure uniformity of distribution of reactant gases, heat and water management, electrical conductivity and mechanical stability. Non-ideal distribution of these quantities can lead to degradation of the parts of the FC concerned [9–14]. A number of studies have focused on the impact of various flow-field designs [15–22], channel-to-rib width ratio [18,19,23–27], channel height [18,24,28], and cross-section [12,18,25,28–32], among others, on FC performance. Lower channel height increases the gas velocity, thus improving the mass transfer towards the porous layers and removal of water [17,24,28]. Furthermore, lower channel height leads to thinner BPs with higher volumetric power density. On the other hand, decreasing the channel height increases the pressure drop and, consequently the power requirements of the gas compressors [33]. Regarding the rib parameters, their width affects the extent of the under-the-rib convection, thus influencing the mass transport to and from the catalyst layer [19,20,23,31]. Therefore, narrower ribs are generally

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: halam@vscht.cz (M. Hala), kodymr@vscht.cz (R. Kodým), prokopm@vscht.cz (M. Prokop), paidarm@vscht.cz (M. Paidar), katie.mccay@sintef.no (K. McCay), luca.ansaloni@sintef.no (L. Ansaloni), bouzekk@vscht.cz (K. Bouzek).

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Nomenclature			
a_{spec}	Specific area of catalyst surface ($\text{m}^2 \text{m}^{-3}$)	$V_{f,i/e,CL}$	Volumetric fraction of the ion/electron conductive phase in CL
CFA	Angle of the channel flank ($^\circ$)	$x_{i/k}$	Molar fraction of species i/k
CG	Channel ground width (m)	<i>Greek Letters</i>	
c_i	Molar concentration of species i (mol m^{-3})	$\alpha_{a,o}$	Anode oxidation direction charge transfer coefficient
$c_{i,\text{ref}}$	Reference molar concentration of species I (mol m^{-3})	$\alpha_{a,r}$	Anode reduction direction charge transfer coefficient
CP	Channel rib width (m)	$\alpha_{c,o}$	Cathode oxidation direction charge transfer coefficient
CR	Radius (m)	$\alpha_{c,r}$	Cathode reduction direction charge transfer coefficient
CRW	Channel and rib width (m)	ε	Porosity
CW	Channel width (m)	κ	Tensor of permeability (m^2)
D	Diffusivity ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	λ_i	Stoichiometric excess of species i
\mathbf{d}	Diffusional driving force (m^{-1})	μ	Fluid dynamic viscosity (Pa s)
\mathbf{D}	Diffusivity matrix ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	ρ	Density (kg m^{-3})
$\mathbf{D}_{\text{eff},i}$	Effective multicomponent Maxwell-Stefan diffusivity matrix of species i ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	$\sigma_{i/e}$	Specific ionic/electronic conductivity (S m^{-1})
$\mathbf{D}_{\text{eff},ik}$	Effective multicomponent Maxwell-Stefan diffusivity ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	$\varphi_{i/e}$	Ionic/electronic potential (V)
\mathbf{D}_{ik}	Multicomponent Maxwell-Stefan diffusivity ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	$\omega_{i/k}$	Mass fraction of species i/k
E	Electrode potential (V)	<i>Indexes</i>	
$E_{\text{eq},a/c}$	Equilibrium anode/cathode potential (V)	o	Exchange
$E_{r,\text{HOR}}$	Reversible electrode potential of hydrogen oxidation reaction (V)	a	Anode
$E_{r,\text{ORR}}$	Reversible electrode potential of oxygen reduction reaction (V)	A	Absolute
\mathcal{F}	Faraday constant (C mol^{-1})	applied	Applied
$F_{a/c,\text{inlet}}$	Mass flow rate (kg s^{-1})	BP	Bipolar plate
h_{BP}	Thickness of the BP (m)	c	Cathode
h_{CL}	Thickness of the CL (m)	CL	Catalyst layer
h_{GDL}	Thickness of the GDL (m)	corr	Corrected
h_{MEM}	Thickness of the MEM (m)	e	Electron
h_{MPL}	Thickness of the MPL (m)	eff	Effective
CH	Channel height (m)	eq	Equilibrium
\mathbf{I}	Identity matrix	f	Fraction
I_{applied}	Applied current (A)	GDL	Gas diffusion layer
\mathbf{j}	Current density (A m^{-2})	H	Hydrogen
$j_{0,\text{ref},\text{HOR}}$	Hydrogen oxidation reaction reference exchange current density (A m^{-2})	HOR	Hydrogen oxidation reaction
$j_{0,\text{ref},\text{ORR}}$	Oxygen reduction reaction reference exchange current density (A m^{-2})	i	Species i
\mathbf{j}_e	Current density vector in electron-conductive phase (A m^{-2})	i	Ionic
\mathbf{J}_i	Mass flux of species i ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)	in	Inner
\mathbf{j}_i	Current density vector in ion-conductive phase (A m^{-2})	inlet	Inlet
$j_{s,a/c}$	Current density on catalyst surface (anode/cathode) (A m^{-2})	IP	In-plane
$M_{a,c,\text{inlet}}$	Mean molecular weight of cathode/anode inlet gas	k	Species k
$M_{i/k}$	Molecular weight of species i/k (kg mol^{-1})	m	Mass
N	Number of nodal points	MEM	Membrane
p	Fluid pressure (Pa)	MPL	Microporous layer
\mathcal{R}	Universal gas constant ($\text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$)	N	Nitrogen
S_m	Mass source term ($\text{kg m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$)	O	Oxygen
S_q	Charge source term ($\text{C m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$)	ORR	Oxygen reduction reaction
T	Temperature (K)	out	Outer
\mathbf{u}	Fluid velocity vector (m s^{-1})	q	Charge
		r	Reversible
		ref	Reference
		s	Surface
		spec	Specific
		TP	Through-plane
		Wa	Water

considered beneficial, although interfacial contact resistance and gas diffusion layer (GDL) intrusion need to be taken into account [34]. However, in some cases, low channel to rib width ration is beneficial from uniformity of species distribution [19]. The cross-sectional geometry of the channel influences the gas velocity profile [29]. The diffusion of species through the GDL to the catalyst layer alone is slow, thus forced convection highly improves the species transport. Therefore,

intensification of gas convection in the GDL, while keeping the pressure drop to the minimum, is the aim of BP design optimization. Additionally, flow-field designs, such as parallel, serpentine or interdigitated, can have completely different effects on the dimensions of the ideal channel geometry, as they have a great influence on the pressure drop, velocity profile and distribution of species [18–20,28,29,35]. The performance of the investigated FC design is influenced by a multitude of

counteracting factors, making accurate prediction challenging without appropriate analysis for each instance.

Mathematical modelling is a time-efficient and economical method of studying the effects of BP geometries on the distribution of local quantities, which are technically demanding and time-consuming to obtain experimentally with sufficient resolution. Several mathematical models exist, describing different aspects of PEM FCs in various levels of detail [3,16–20,23–29,31,36–39]. Currently, the most popular models are three-dimensional (3D), single-cell, steady-state and single-phase (or simplified multi-phase), because of their sufficiently accurate results and acceptable demands on computer hardware power. Within the last decade, efficient mathematical models of PEM FC stacks of industrially relevant size have appeared as well [15,40,41]. However, only a limited number of modelling studies focuses on stamped BPs [7,30,42,43], focusing on the manufacturability of the proposed geometries and flow distribution, both highlighting the need for further analysis for this specific case.

The geometry of the cross-section of metallic BP's flow field channels produced by high-capacity methods differs from the traditional rectangular shape with sharp edges and high aspect ratio. According to the best of the authors' knowledge, a direct comparison between these two types of cross-section geometries has not yet been done. The target of this study is to fill this knowledge gap by gaining a deeper understanding of the impact of the stamped channels' cross-section geometry on the local distribution of physico-chemical quantities in a PEM FC using mathematical modelling of 3D continuum-mechanics. Altogether, nine variations of BP cross-section geometry for each milled, stamped, straight and serpentine FF were analysed. The results allow to optimize the BP's cross-section geometry within the framework of its manufacturability contributing to a further development of mass production of PEM FCs.

2. Experimental

2.1. Determination of kinetic parameters and model validation

A modified simplified single fuel cell was constructed in order to record experimental load curves allowing the determination of the electrode reaction kinetics parameters needed for the mathematical modelling. This fuel cell uses planar-plate current collectors/feeders, substituting the bipolar plates. Dural endplates equipped with heating cartridges and thermocouples were used for cell temperature control. 1 mm and 0.5 mm thick expanded PTFE gaskets (KWO) were used to seal the membrane-electrode assembly. 3 mm thick hydrophilic carbon felt (Mersen) was used to ensure reactant distribution to the electrodes and to provide electronic contact between current collectors and electrodes. Carbon felt was chosen instead of the standard flow-field channels approach, as it significantly lowers the manufacturing time, cost. Moreover, in case of small active area the difference in pressure loss and homogeneity in local distribution of quantities can be considered negligible when compared to the standard approach. For more detailed information on cell construction see Fig. 1.

Sigracet 28BC (SGL) carbon paper with a microporous layer was used as a gas diffusion layer. Catalyst-coated membranes were prepared by ultrasonic-assisted deposition of a catalyst ink onto the membrane. Catalyst HisPEC 4000 (Johnson-Matthey) with 40 % platinum on carbon, Nafion D521 (Chemours) 5 % binder dispersion in isopropanol and acetone was used as an ink. The targeted loading was $0.3 \text{ mg Pt cm}^{-2}$. Nafion 212 (Chemours) was used as the membrane. The dimensions of the active area were 5 cm by 1 cm.

The corresponding test bench used to operate the cell is shown in Fig. 2. Mass flow controllers (Bronkhorst) were used to control the gas feed. Incoming gases were humidified at laboratory temperature using Nafion tubing (Permapure) submerged in deionised water. PGSTAT302N potentiostat with a 20 A booster (Autolab) was used for fuel cell characterization. The cells were operated in galvanostatic regime at 0.5 A cm^{-2} for a total of 24 h. After 24 h the load curve

Fig. 1. A) Exploded view of the experimental PEM fuel cell used for kinetic parameters measurements. B) Photo of a completed cell.

measurement ranging from open circuit voltage to 0.25 V was recorded. The measurement was done twice and every experiment was repeated five times. The average values of these results up to 3 A cm^{-2} were used for the validation of the mathematical model.

3. Numerical model

The mathematical model employed was 3D, stationary and isothermal, based on a continuum mechanics model approach. Load curves, local current densities, concentrations of species and velocities of gases were calculated. Parametric studies were performed to compare different cross-section geometries with various dimensional parameters. The model includes mass and charge transport in a single cell of a low temperature PEM FC. The gas diffusion electrode was treated by means of a macro-homogeneous approach (porous electrode theory [44], and the anisotropy in through- and in-plane permeability is considered). Compression of GDL under the BP rib was considered as well. The Brinkman and Navier-Stokes equations were employed to describe fluid flow in a porous environment and a free channel volume, respectively. Multicomponent transport was described by the dusty-gas model (including simplified Stefan-Maxwell equations and Knudsen diffusion).

3.1. Numerical model assumptions

The following assumptions are considered in the presented model:

- the system operates in steady-state,
- the system is isothermal,
- the gas mixtures are ideal,

Fig. 2. A) FC testing station connection diagram. B) Photography of the FC testing station.

- the fluid flow is single-phase (gas), i.e., water condensation is neglected,
- the fluids are Newtonian and incompressible for the case of momentum conservation,
- the membrane is considered gas-tight and homogeneous with constant specific conductivity,
- the material, and therefore the electrical conductivity, of BPs with both stamped and milled channels is considered to be gold coated stainless steel.

The system was assumed to be isothermal due to the small size of the

modelled geometry and use of a current range causing no extreme local heating. For the same reasons, the membrane conductivity was considered to be homogeneous over its entire active area. Water condensation can be neglected as it was not observed in the experiment. It is mainly due to using dry oxygen in large excess on the cathode side of the cell. The effect of condensation is considered in the results discussion. The incompressibility of the gaseous reactants is assumed because the pressure difference between the inlet and outlet in the studied cases did not exceed 720 Pa, which is negligible with respect to the absolute pressure. The gas-tightness of the membrane is assumed due to having a small effect on the studied parameters. Stainless steel grade SS 316 L

Fig. 3. Studied rib geometries and descriptive parameters for A) stamped channel, B) milled channel. C) Description of the FC layers. The studied stamped flow-field designs: D) straight channel, E) serpentine channel. For values of individual geometric parameters see Table 1. Different types of model boundaries with special boundary conditions: F) view from the gas inlet, G) view from the gas outlet; red – current inlet (from anode side), orange – current outlet (from cathode side), light green – gas inlet, dark green – gas outlet, pink – slip boundaries, blue – symmetry boundaries (for the colours, see the on-line version of the paper).

with gold coating to minimize interfacial contact resistance, as it was used in the experiment.

3.2. Geometry configurations

The model PEM FC geometry consists of 11 distinct domains – BPs, GDLs, microporous layers (MPLs) and catalyst layers (CLs) for both anode and cathode, and a proton-conducting membrane (MEM). Milled and stamped BPs with two types of flow-field designs, parallel and serpentine, were studied. Flow channels represent the additional two model domains. The studied BP designs and parameters used to describe the BP cross-section geometry are shown in Fig. 3. Table 1 summarizes the main parameters of the two geometry designs. Seven parameters are used to parametrically describe the shape of the stamped BP flow field cross-section [34], while only four parameters are sufficient to describe the milled. During the parametric study, the channel and rib width were varied with a total of 9 combinations of the values 0.2, 1 and 2 mm for each of the parameters. Values of CFA, CR_{in} and CR_{out} were chosen under consideration of the material constraints of the metals [7].

3.3. Governing equations

3.3.1. Fluid flow

3.3.1.1. Momentum conservation. The fluid flow on the anode and cathode side of the cell is described by means of Brinkman Equations (see Equations (1) and (2)). They extend the Navier-Stokes equation for a porous environment, where the Darcy's law term accounts for the viscous friction exerted by porous material in the momentum balance. These equations treat both the hydraulic pressure p and the flow velocity vector \mathbf{u} as dependent variables. For the case of momentum conservation, the gases in both electrodes are considered incompressible. This is a reasonable assumption since the pressure difference between the inlet and outlet is relatively low with respect to the absolute pressure, thus the gas density ρ gradients are relatively small with negligible effect on the fluid momentum.

$$\frac{1}{\epsilon} \rho (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} \frac{1}{\epsilon} = \nabla [-p\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{K}] - \left(\mu \boldsymbol{\kappa}^{-1} + \frac{S_m}{\epsilon^2} \right) \mathbf{u} \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{K} = \frac{\mu}{\epsilon} (\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T) - \frac{2}{3} \frac{\mu}{\epsilon} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) \mathbf{I} \quad (2)$$

The remaining symbols in the above Brinkman equations are as follows: ϵ denotes porosity of the porous layer (GDL, MPL, CL), μ is fluid dynamic viscosity, $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ represents hydraulic permeability tensor of the porous material, S_m stands for mass source in the electrodes and \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix.

3.3.1.2. Mass conservation. The mass balance, both in the anode and

Table 1
Description of the base-case cross-sectional geometric parameters.

Parameter	Value stamped / milled BP	Description
CH	0.5 mm	Channel height
CRW	3.2 / 2 mm	Total channel width
CR _{in}	0.2 / – mm	Inner radius
CR _{out}	0.4 / – mm	Outer radius
CFA	20°	Angle of the channel flank
CG	1 mm	Channel ground width
CP	1 mm	Rib width
CW	2.2 / – mm	Channel width
h _{BP}	0.2 mm / 1 mm	Thickness of the BP
h _{GDL}	0.145 mm	Thickness of the GDL [45]
h _{MPL}	0.055 mm	Thickness of the MPL [45]
h _{CL}	0.004 mm	Thickness of the CL [46]
h _{MEM}	0.050 mm	Thickness of the MEM

cathode streams, is described by Equation (3). The electrode reactions affect the local flow hydrodynamics of the gas due to the consumption of oxygen and hydrogen, and the production of water, as characterized by the source term in this mass balance equation.

$$\begin{aligned} S_m &= \left(-\frac{S_q M_{H_2}}{2\mathcal{F}} \right) (anode) \\ \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) &= S_m; \\ S_m &= \left(-\frac{S_q M_{H_2O}}{2\mathcal{F}} + \frac{S_q M_{O_2}}{4\mathcal{F}} \right) (cathode) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Here M identifies the molecular weight of the respective gas component (see subscript), \mathcal{F} is Faraday's constant and S_q represents the charge source term in the charge conservation in the porous electrode.

3.3.2. Charge flow

3.3.2.1. Charge conservation. The conservation of electric charge-flow in the cell is described by Equations (4) to (7). In the case of the catalyst layer, porous electrode theory is employed. The charge transfer across the electroactive surface mediated by electrode reactions is described by reaction charge source S_q in the porous catalyst layers domains. S_q is zero in the other domains of the FC model. Equation (6) describing S_q considers the specific area of the catalyst a_{spec} (more precisely, the specific three-phase boundary area) and the reaction current density $j_{s,r}$ ($r = a, c$) of the main electrode reaction taking place on the catalyst surface. In Equations (4) and (5), \mathbf{j}_i and \mathbf{j}_e describe the local current density (intensity of electric charge flux) in the ion-conductive domain and the electron-conductive domain, respectively. These local current densities are proportional to the electric potential gradients and to the effective specific conductivity of the materials used as described by Equation (7). For the prediction of effective conductivities, the Bruggeman equation is used, which predicts tortuosity of random porous material on the basis of its porosity ϵ .

$$-\nabla \cdot \mathbf{j}_i + S_q = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$-\nabla \cdot \mathbf{j}_e - S_q = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$S_q = a_{spec} j_{s,r}, r = a, c \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{j}_{i/e} = -\epsilon^{3/2} \sigma_{i/e} \nabla \phi_{i/e} \quad (7)$$

3.3.2.2. Electrode reaction kinetics. The current density of the electrode reaction on the anode catalyst surface ($j_{s,a}$) is described using a linearized kinetic equation (Equation (8)) and on the cathode catalyst surface ($j_{s,c}$) by the Butler-Volmer kinetic equation (Equation (9)) as used and recommended e.g. in [47]. The local reversible equilibrium electrode potentials ($E_{eq,a}$, $E_{eq,c}$) are described by Nernst equations (Equations (10) and (11)). They vary with a change of local reactant molar concentrations c_i .

$$j_{s,a} = j_{0,HOR} \left(\frac{c_{H_2}}{c_{H_2,ref}} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} (\alpha_{a,o} + \alpha_{a,r}) \frac{\mathcal{F}}{\mathcal{R}T} (E - E_{eq,a}) \quad (8)$$

$$j_{s,c} = j_{0,ORR} \left(\frac{c_{O_2}}{c_{O_2,ref}} \right)^{1 - \frac{\alpha_{c,r}}{4}} \left(\exp \left(\frac{\alpha_{c,o} \mathcal{F}}{\mathcal{R}T} (E - E_{eq,c}) \right) - \exp \left(\frac{-\alpha_{c,r} \mathcal{F}}{\mathcal{R}T} (E - E_{eq,c}) \right) \right) \quad (9)$$

$$E_{eq,a} = -\frac{\mathcal{R}T}{2\mathcal{F}} \ln \left(\frac{c_{H_2}}{c_{H_2,ref}} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$E_{eq,c} = U_{OCV} - \frac{\mathcal{R}T}{4\mathcal{F}} \ln \left(\frac{c_{O_2}}{c_{O_2,ref}} \right) \quad (11)$$

$c_{i,\text{ref}}$ represents reference concentration of the i -th component. Furthermore, E denotes electrode potential $E = \phi_e - \phi_i$, \mathcal{R} universal gas constant and T is thermodynamic temperature. The kinetic parameters of electrode reactions are $\alpha_{r,s}$ ($r = a, c; s = o, r$) representing coefficients of charge transfer in the oxidation and reduction direction, respectively, and $j_{0,\text{HOR}}$ and $j_{0,\text{ORR}}$ refers to the exchange current densities of hydrogen oxidation reaction (HOR) and oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) respectively.

3.3.3. Multicomponent mass transport

3.3.3.1. Species conservation. The conservation of $N-1$ gaseous components (where N is the total number of components in the mixture) is described by Equation (12), where ω_i and \mathbf{J}_i represent mass fraction and relative mass flux of the i -th component, respectively. The N -th component mass fraction is then computed using Equation (13). Molar fraction x_i and mass fraction ω_i of individual components is calculated using Equation (14), while the mean molecular weight is calculated using Equation (15).

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_i + \rho(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \omega_i = S_m \quad (12)$$

$$\omega_N = 1 - \sum_{i=2}^{N-1} \omega_i \quad (13)$$

$$x_i = \frac{\omega_i \bar{M}}{M_i} \quad (14)$$

$$\bar{M} = \left(\sum_i \frac{\omega_i}{M_i} \right)^{-1} = \sum_{i=1}^N x_i M_i \quad (15)$$

3.3.3.2. Species transport equations. Multicomponent mass transport in the free channel volume is described by the Stefan-Maxwell diffusion model. The relative mass flux vector \mathbf{J}_i in the channels is described by Equation (16). The diffusional driving force \mathbf{d}_k is calculated using Equation (17). The effective binary Stefan-Maxwell diffusion coefficients $D_{\text{eff},ik}$ are calculated with Equation (18). The Stefan-Maxwell diffusivities are calculated using kinetic gas theory, as described in [48].

$$\mathbf{J}_i = - \left(\rho \omega_i \sum_k D_{\text{eff},ik} \mathbf{d}_k \right) \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbf{d}_k = \nabla x_k + \frac{1}{p_A} [(x_k - \omega_k) \nabla p] \quad (17)$$

$$D_{\text{eff},ik} = \epsilon^{3/2} D_{ik} \quad (18)$$

3.3.4. Complementary equations

The porosity and height of the compressed GDL was approximated using Equation (19) and Equation (20), respectively. As a measure of GDL compression, a parameter $Comp$ was introduced. The value of $Comp = 0$ relates to uncompressed GDL, the value of $Comp = 0.25$ means that the GDL was compressed to 75 % of its original thickness as calculated by Equation (20). This value was obtained experimentally.

$$\epsilon = 1 - \frac{1 - \epsilon_{\text{GDL}}}{1 - Comp} \quad (19)$$

$$h_{\text{GDL,compressed}} = h_{\text{GDL}} (1 - Comp) \quad (20)$$

In these equations the parameters ϵ_{GDL} and h_{GDL} represent the initial uncompressed porosity and height of the GDL, respectively. The compression of other porous layers (MPL, CL) was neglected in this work, because it does not have a major impact on the fluid flow inside the fuel cell and it unnecessarily complicates the parameter input.

3.4. Boundary conditions

The types of individual boundaries used in the model are schematically indicated in Fig. 3. Regarding mass balance, a mass inflow of the oxidant and fuel gases on the gas inlet boundaries is bound with calculated current I_{applied} passing through the cell by means of Faraday's law as given in Equation (21). This is because a fixed stoichiometric excess of oxygen λ_O and hydrogen λ_H is employed at each value of applied current. At the gas outlets a value of hydraulic pressure is set at the constant reference pressure. Furthermore, mass fractions of all components are fixed at the gas inlet boundary (see Equation (22) according to the inlet composition used in the model FC.

With respect to the charge flux and electric field description, the model operates in a potentiostatic mode, so, the cell voltage is controlled. At the current outlet boundary (at the cathode) the electric potential $\phi_{e,\text{outlet}}$ is set to the parametrically changing value of voltage U , while at the current inlet (at the anode) boundary the electric potential $\phi_{e,\text{inlet}}$ is set to 0 V as described by Equation (23). The passing current I_{applied} (as used in Equation (21) is then calculated, in every iteration and every value of U , by surface integration of normal current density \mathbf{j}_e at the current inlet boundary.

At the rest of the boundaries a) zero fluxes of components, mass and electric charge are considered, with no slip boundary conditions, or b) symmetric boundary conditions are applied as shown in Fig. 3.

$$F_{c/a,\text{inlet}} = \frac{I_{\text{applied}}}{\mathcal{F} \lambda_{O/H}} \lambda_{O/H} M_{c/a,\text{inlet}} \quad (21)$$

$$\omega_i = \omega_{i,\text{in}} \quad (22)$$

$$\phi_{e,\text{outlet}} = U, \quad \phi_{e,\text{inlet}} = 0 \text{ V} \quad (23)$$

3.5. Model summary

COMSOL Multiphysics 6.0 software was used to solve the set of partial differential equations (conservation laws, constitutive transport equations, etc.) using the finite elements method. The model consists of 10 dependent variables, namely 2 electronic and ionic electric potentials, 3 components of gas velocity vector, gas pressure and 4 species mass fractions. The charge flow partial differential equations were implemented using the "General Form PDE" COMSOL interface, the fluid flow through the Brinkman Equations interface, and multicomponent mass transport through the Transport of Concentrated Species interface. The structural, transport and operating parameters used are summarized in Table 3 and Table 4. The model equations were solved

Table 2
Kinetic parameters used for calculations.

Parameter	Value	Description
$j_{0,\text{HOR}}$	$1000 j_{0,\text{ref,ORR}}$	Hydrogen oxidation reaction exchange current density, (fitted)
$j_{0,\text{ORR}}$	0.11 A m^{-2}	Oxygen reduction reaction exchange current density (fitted)
$c_{\text{H}_2,\text{ref}}$	41.5 mol m^{-3}	H_2 reference concentration
$c_{\text{O}_2,\text{ref}}$	8.7 mol m^{-3}	O_2 reference concentration
$\alpha_{a,r}$	0.5	Anode – reduction direction charge transfer coefficient [47]
$\alpha_{c,r}$	1	Cathode – reduction direction charge transfer coefficient [47]
$\alpha_{a,o}$	0.5	Anode – oxidation direction charge transfer coefficient [47]
$\alpha_{c,o}$	3	Cathode – oxidation direction charge transfer coefficient [47]
U_{OCV}	0.964 V	Reversible open circuit voltage (fitted)
a_{Pt}	$60 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$	Platinum catalyst specific area (estimate)
m_{Pt}	0.3 mg cm^{-2}	Platinum catalyst loading at anode / cathode
a_{spec}	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^{-1}$	Specific surface area, calculated from a_{Pt} and m_{Pt}
R_{corr}	0.42725	Felt resistance correction factor (fitted)

Table 3
Structural and transport parameters used for calculations.

Parameter	Value	Description
ϵ_{CL}	0.45	Porosity of CL [46]
ϵ_{MPL}	0.72	Porosity of MPL [46]
ϵ_{GDL}	0.75	Porosity of GDL [46]
$V_{i,CL}$	0.4	Volumetric fraction of the ion-conductive phase in CL
$V_{e,CL}$	0.4	Volumetric fraction of the electron-conductive phase in CL
$\sigma_{TP,GDL}$	300 S m^{-1}	GDL through-plane specific conductivity (as measured)
$\sigma_{IP,GDL}$	$20,000 \text{ S m}^{-1}$	GDL in-plane specific conductivity (as measured)
σ_{SS}	$1.45 \cdot 10^6 \text{ S m}^{-1}$	Stainless steel specific conductivity [49]
σ_{MEM}	5 S m^{-1}	Membrane ionic conductivity [50]
σ_{MPL}	1000 S m^{-1}	MPL specific conductivity (estimate)
σ_{CL}	300 S m^{-1}	CL specific conductivity (as measured)
$\sigma_{FELT,corr}$	$3000 \frac{1}{R_{corr}} \text{ S m}^{-1}$	Carbon felt specific conductivity (used for fitting)
σ_i	2.125 S m^{-1}	Ionic specific conductivity (calculated)
$\kappa_{GDL,IP}$	$2.8 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$	GDL hydraulic permeability, in-plane [51]
$\kappa_{GDL,TP}$	$0.47 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$	GDL hydraulic permeability, through-plane [51]
κ_{MPL}	$2.8 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$	MPL hydraulic permeability [51]
κ_{CL}	$0.1 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$	CL hydraulic permeability (estimate)
μ	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ Pa s}$	Gas dynamic viscosity
$Comp$	0.25	Compression of GDL under ribs

Table 4
Operating parameters used for calculations.

Parameter	Value	Description
T	$80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	Operating temperature
P	1.1 atm	Operating pressure
$x_{inlet,H}$	0.9	Hydrogen inlet molar fraction
$x_{inlet,Wa}$	0.1	Anode water inlet molar fraction
$x_{inlet,O}$	0.21	Oxygen inlet molar fraction
$x_{inlet,N}$	0.789	Nitrogen inlet molar fraction
$x_{inlet,W}$	0.001	Cathode water inlet molar fraction
λ_O	4	Oxygen stoichiometric excess ratio
λ_H	2	Hydrogen stoichiometric excess ratio

using the ‘‘Fully Coupled method’’ with ‘‘Direct linear solver’’ with 0.001 relative tolerance on a computer with two Intel® Xeon® E5-2643 3.4 GHz CPUs, 512 GB of 2133 MHz RAM and NVIDIA GeForce GTX 750 Ti graphics card. The average calculation time was 57 min for the straight channels and 30 h for the serpentine channels.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Electrode reactions kinetics and model validation

In the first step, mathematical model developed was used to simulate behaviour of the fuel cell used for characterisation of the developed bipolar plates. Beside validation of the modelling approach proposed, the aim was to fit the electrode reactions kinetics to be used in the later steps of this study.

Resulting experimental data are shown, together with the model results, in Fig. 4. Due to the simplified geometry of the experimental system and large excess of reactants, one-dimensional (1D) continuum-mechanics model was used in this particular case allowing rapid calculation and thus iteration of kinetic parameters. The values of the charge transfer coefficients $\alpha_{r,s}$ ($r = a, c; s = o, r$) were adopted from the literature [47]. The 1D model used only considers carbon felt, GDLs, MPLs, CL, and the membrane as model domains. Otherwise, the model is identical to the 3D model described in chapter 3 of this study. MATLAB built-in optimization function ‘‘patternsearch’’ (based on a non-linear constrained optimization method) was utilized in order to minimize the standard deviation between the modelled and experimental load

Fig. 4. Load curve of simplified single FC cell designed for kinetic measurements: red circles – averaged experimental data with error bars indicating standard deviation, blue curve – fitted model curve.

curves. The fitted and experimental load curves are shown in Fig. 4. The kinetic parameter values obtained are summarized in Table 2 provided above.

The agreement between the experimental and the model data was very good ($R^2 = 0.9980$), confirming the model to be able to describe fuel cell operation with sufficient accuracy. At the same time it proves the exchange current density was successfully fitted. To match the slope of the experimental load curves in the ohmic region, the use of a correction coefficient (R_{corr}) was needed. This was due to the variation of the cell ohmic resistance upon its compression, mainly because of the change in the carbon felt electrical conductivity and contact resistance. Fitted value of this parameter was, together with the cell compression, used in the subsequent parts of the study.

4.2. Study on the flow field channels cross-section geometry impact on the fuel cell performance

Two notably different designs of the flow-field were investigated in this study. The results for the parallel straight channels flow-field are presented in section 4.2.1, whereas for the serpentine channel flow-field in section 4.2.2, for both the stamped and milled type of the bipolar plate.

A summary of the values of CP and CG used for the model calculations is presented in Table 5. Corresponding values of CRW are presented as well. These values were selected to represent a wide range of cases which could be compared against each in several ways. Upper limit of 2 mm rib and channel ground width was chosen based on a feasible

Table 5

Comparison between total channel widths (CRW) for different combinations of channel ground (CG) and rib (CP) width. Cases with similar CRW suitable for comparison are Stamped Case 2 (CP = 0.2 mm, CG = 1 mm, CRW = 2.4 mm) and Milled Case 3 (CP = 0.2 mm, CG = 2 mm, CRW = 2.2 mm); Stamped Case 5 (CP = 1 mm, CG = 1 mm, CRW = 3.2 mm) and Milled Case 6 (CP = 1 mm, CG = 2 mm, CRW = 3 mm) and Stamped case 8 (CP = 2 mm, CG = 1 mm, CRW = 4.2 mm) and Milled Case 9 (CP = 2 mm, CG = 2 mm, CRW = 4.2 mm).

Case	CP / mm	CG / mm	CRW / mm stamped	CRW / mm milled
1	0.2	0.2	1.6	0.4
2	0.2	1	2.4	1.2
3	0.2	2	3.4	2.2
4	1	0.2	2.4	1.2
5	1	1	3.2	2
6	1	2	4.2	3
7	2	0.2	3.4	2.2
8	2	1	4.2	3.2
9	2	2	5.2	4.2

model convergence and practical significance. The focus was on these two parameters. Remaining parameters, such as flank angle and channel height, although interesting to investigate, were fixed, as their impact was found to be significantly less important.

4.2.1. Straight channels

The graphs in Fig. 5 A and B demonstrate the impact of varying channel ribs (CP) and ground widths (CG) on the performance of the PEM FC by means of the load curves. The shape of the curves is slightly different when comparing milled channels with a rectangular cross-section and stamped channels with a trapezoidal cross-section. The stamped channels exhibit mass transport limitation even at higher voltages i.e., lower current loads (for the cases 5 and 6 the mass transport limitation occurs at approximately 0.57 V in the case of stamped channels compared to 0.48 V in the case of milled channels). However, the decline in FC performance is only moderate. This effect is related to the fact that the inclined side walls of stamped channels limit the convective flux of the gaseous reactants in the domain close to the wall contact with the GDL. The performance (current density) of the FCs at 0.55 V is summarized in Fig. 6. Overall, milled channels with rectangular cross-section geometry and narrower CP (cases 1–3, 5 and 6, 8 and 9) performed slightly better than the stamped channels.

Considering the channel rib width, the cross-section geometries with

Fig. 6. Current density at 0.55 V for the FCs with straight channels.

Fig. 5. Load curves for A) straight milled channels, B) straight stamped channels, C) straight milled channel with bipolar plate material conductivity set to 100 S cm⁻¹, D) straight hypothetical stamped metallic flow-field with rectangular channel cross-section and sharp corners of the BP mimicking milled channels.

the narrowest ribs performed the best. This is in agreement with the literature, e.g. [23]. However, the manufacture of such narrow channels represents a potential issue from the standpoint of the mechanical stability of steel foil during the formation of such fine structures [52]. An identical effect of CG width on FC performance is observed for the cases of CP = 1 and 2 mm. Interestingly enough, in the case of CP = 0.2 mm, the trend was exactly the opposite, i.e., the FC with CG = 2 mm

performed the worst. Two counteracting effects explain the occurrence of this optimum: current path length and reactant distribution. Both effects will be discussed later in this chapter.

Moreover, in the case of the milled channels, a clear trend of FC performance improvement with decreasing rib width is visible. The transport limitation commences at lower current loads in the case of FCs with wider ribs. The width of the channel ground has the opposite effect.

Fig. 7. Concentration fields of oxygen at the CL/MPL interface in x-y plane for straight milled and stamped channels with three sets of different ribs (CP) and channel (CG) widths at 0.55 V. Minimum and maximum oxygen concentration is shown above the graphs.

The FCs with the widest 2 mm channel performed slightly better than those with 1 mm wide channels and much better than those with 0.2 mm wide channels. In the case of the narrowest ribs of $CP = 0.2$ mm, their performance did not depend on the CG width. This positive impact of wider CG on the FC performance is caused by better distribution of reactants. At the same time, more important transport limitation can be observed for milled channels with the smallest CG, cases 4 and 7, than for stamped channels with the same CG, because of the additional area under the slanted wall of the stamped channels. Therefore, they provide the smallest part of the electrode area supplied well with reactants, as discussed later in the text.

In order to understand the impact of BP material conductivity and channel cross-section geometry on the FC performance, two additional cases are computed to support our discussion. First, a straight milled channel with BP electrical conductivity equal to 100 S cm^{-1} , which is two orders of magnitude lower than the conductivity of stainless steel and is a target value for polymer-carbon composite BPs (see Fig. 5 C). Second, a straight hypothetical stamped metallic flow-field with a rectangular channel cross-section and sharp corners. Lowering the conductivity of the BP from the typical value for SS to 100 S cm^{-1} shows the most important effect on channels with $CP = 0.2$ mm (compare Fig. 5 A and C). This is connected with the fact that the current is passing through a small effective cross-section with relatively low conductivity to reach an electrode. Therefore, in this case, the conductivity of the material is the limiting factor. In the other cases, only insignificant differences are observed, suggesting that mass transport has the predominant effect on performance. For milled channels and a hypothetical stamped metallic flow-field with a rectangular channel cross-section and sharp corners (Fig. 5 A and D), very small differences are observed in cases with $CP = 1$ and 2 mm (less than 0.35 % difference in current density at 0.55 V between the channels with the same CG a CP) and no differences in the case of $CP = 0.2$ mm (the curve for $CP = CG = 0.2$ mm is covered). This documents the fact that, in contrast to the case of the BP material with lower conductivity, the conductivity of the steel is sufficiently high to ensure effective charge distribution and the cross-section geometry of the flow-field channels determines the FC performance.

The above-mentioned observations related to the effects of mass transfer limitation can be clearly explained by means of the calculated concentration fields of oxygen as the reacting gaseous component with the lowest inlet concentration, shown in Fig. 7. In this figure, the oxygen local concentration distribution in the x - y plane at the interface between the CL and the MPL for straight milled and stamped channels is shown. The results are compared for three sets of parameters ($CP = CG = 0.2$ or 2 mm for both geometries and $CP = 1$ and $CG = 2$ mm where $CRW = 3$ mm for milled and $CP = CG = 1$ mm where $CRW = 3.2$ mm for stamped).

The oxygen concentration field corresponds to a cell voltage of 0.55 V. With increasing width of the rib, the concentration of oxygen under the rib decreases. For the lowest CP and CG cases ($CP = CG = 0.2$ mm), the concentration of oxygen remains practically constant in the radial direction (i.e., along y coordinate at the CL/MPL interface) and decreases almost linearly from the inlet to the outlet in the direction of the gas flow (i.e., in axial direction along the x coordinate). This indicates that the channel rib of this width does not represent a significant barrier to the transport of oxygen. Therefore, the concentration field below the rib is homogeneous. However, with increasing CP the concentration decrease under the ribs becomes much more profound than in the channel region, i.e., concentration gradients in the radial direction also become pronounced. In the cases of $CP = 2$ mm, the concentration of oxygen in the under-the-rib area already reaches 0 mol m^{-3} . This is because of negligible convective flow in the GDL taking place in this particular flow-field geometry (straight channels). Diffusion in the GDL as the only means of mass transport in the case of straight channels, is not fast enough to provide sufficient reactant flow intensity. This effect appears for the rib width of 1 mm and wider. The area with depleted oxygen further grows with increasing cell load. This explains the positive impact of the rib width reduction on the FC performance pointed out above. As can be seen in Fig. 8, the concentration of hydrogen changes mainly in the x axial-direction and even the areas in the middle of ribs are sufficiently supplied. The reason is that, in the case of hydrogen, no inert component (nitrogen) is present in the stream, diluting the reactant, and also due to the higher diffusivity of hydrogen when compared to oxygen. Therefore, in the cases studied limitation due to low oxygen concentration always occurs before any critical limitation to the hydrogen supply starts to be noticeable.

Contrary to the under-the-rib area, the area under the channel is always significantly better supplied with oxygen. Therefore, in the case of CPs = 1 and 2 mm, the increase in the CG also increases the active area and thus the FC performance.

When comparing milled and stamped channels, the area under the ribs was subjected to greater oxygen transport limitations in the cases of stamped channels, as seen in Fig. 7. This is observed both in the cases of channels with the same CP and CG and with similar CRW. It is also this aspect that contributes to the slightly lower performance of stamped channels with $CP = 1$ mm and $CG = 1$ and 2 mm when compared to milled channels. As transport limitation is not pronounced in the cases with $CP = 0.2$ mm, the higher ohmic resistance caused by a smaller active cross-section area of the stamped BPs is responsible for their slightly worse performance. For the cases with $CG = 0.2$ mm and $CP = 2$ and 1 mm, the additional area under the channel flank in the stamped channels is advantageous as it increases the area with oxygen supply.

Fig. 8. Concentration of hydrogen in the FCs with straight milled and stamped channel at 0.55 V for $CP = 1$ mm and $CG = 2$ mm ($CRW = 3$ mm) for milled channel and $CP = CG = 1$ mm ($CRW = 3.2$ mm) for stamped channel.

However, when comparing the cases with similar CP and CRW, the performance of the stamped channels is worse as the concentration under the ribs declines. This is primarily due to slower convective flux in the areas below the channel flank.

Fig. 9 compares the velocity profiles of the stamped and milled channels with identical CP and with similar CRW. The velocity profiles of both channels are qualitatively similar; exhibiting the highest velocity in the centre of the channel, decreasing towards the channel walls. However, in the case of the stamped channel, there is a larger area of low velocity close to the channel-rib-GDL interface due to the slanting flank. Furthermore, there is an additional area under the inner radius of the channel CR_{in} , under which the partially compressed GDL has poor access to the fast-flowing gases in the channel. These two effects lead to lower concentrations of oxygen under the ribs and, therefore, the occurrence of transport limitations at lower current loads for the BP with the stamped channels. However, when comparing channels with similar CRW, the area of the stamped channel cross-section is smaller, leading to higher flow velocities inside the channel and close to the GDL under the channel. This effect, according to literature [29], improves the removal of the potential liquid water formed in porous layers in this area (not taken into account in the presented model). In the present case, higher cathode gas velocity does not lead to any improvement, as even the lower gas velocity in the case of milled channels is sufficient to keep the oxygen concentration homogeneous. Enhanced gas flow velocity in the y-z direction around the channels' inner radius (at channel-rib-GDL interface) is observed at the middle of the channel and particularly at the outlet in the case of the stamped channels (see Fig. 9 D). This is caused by lower oxygen partial pressure under the rib.

Fig. 9. Velocity profiles of cathodic gas in the FCs with straight milled – A), C) and stamped channels – B), D) at 0.55 V for CP = 1 mm and CG = 2 mm (CRW = 3 mm) for the milled channel and CP = CG = 1 mm (CRW = 3.2 mm) for the stamped channel. A) and B) show gas velocity in three positions in the x-direction (from the inlet to the outlet), C) and D) show gas velocity in yz-direction (perpendicular to x-direction). The current density for the FC with a milled channel is 1.26 A cm^{-2} and 1.16 A cm^{-2} for a stamped channel.

Fig. 10 documents the effect of the cross-section geometry and of the oxygen concentration on relative local current densities (RLCD) (i.e., local current density divided by mean applied current density) for the case of the stamped channel with three sets of channel width parameters. The geometries with high values of CP and CG have much larger areas with lowered local current densities under the rib. This is caused by the low concentration of reactants in this region, as discussed above. In the case of the widest CP, this leads to the local current density under the rib reaching only one third of the value observed under the channel. This causes low utilization of the expensive catalyst in the CL. Oxygen starvation may also lead to enhanced local catalyst degradation.

The homogeneity of the RLCD can be classified using Equation (25), where N is the number of nodal points, j_{local} is the local current density at the nodal point, $j_{average}$ is the average current density. The lower the deviation value, the higher the homogeneity of RLCD. This means that, if the deviation is equal to zero, all the RLCDs are equal over the entire active cell area. The calculated RLCD is shown in three different cell slices: at the CL/MEM boundary, the MPL/GDL boundary and at 75 % of GDL thickness. The last slice represents the BP/GDL boundary in the areas where GDL is compressed, i.e., under the channel ribs. It is evident that the distribution of RLCD becomes more homogeneous closer to the membrane. On the other hand, the most inhomogeneous RLCD distribution can be observed at the contact of the GDL to the BP. This is due to the relatively high in-plane electrical conductivity of the GDL and a relatively small contact area with the BP. The highest current densities are observed in the area under the inner BP radius. The reason is that most of the current collected over the part of the electrode facing the channel passes through this narrow area. In the other layers, the homogeneity of the distribution does not change as significantly as in the GDL. This shows that the uniformity of local current density is significantly affected by the reactant concentration, i.e., by the effectivity of the transport of reactants to the region under the ribs and not by the transport of the electric charge.

$$deviation = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum (j_{local} - j_{average})^2} \quad (25)$$

There is an optimum of the CG width, in the cases of both stamped and milled channels with low conductivity it corresponds to the low values of CP = 0.2 mm. This is because at higher values of CG (relative to CP value) ohmic resistance to charge transport through the BP and porous layers under the channel starts to limit the process. This causes a non-uniform distribution of current density in the GDL and poorer utilization of the CL in the area facing the centre of the channel. This is indicated mainly by a higher slope in the ohmic region of the load curve, see Fig. 5 B) and C) case 3. Furthermore, a too wide CG could lead to non-optimal contact of the GDL and CL or damage to the GDL caused by its intrusion into the channel [34]. As the present results suggest, from the mass transport point of view, the optimum value of the CP value is as low as 0.2 mm. However, this represents a potential problem for manufacturing, contact resistance and GDL damage. Cross-section geometry this fine would increase the manufacturing costs because of the required precision. Furthermore, the risk of mechanical damage during manufacturing would increase substantially. However, thin BPs with a value of CP = 0.4 mm represent a suitable alternative [52]. This value is also acceptable from the point of view of FC operation, because the performance would decrease by less than 8 % compared to a FC with CP = 0.2 mm while operating at 0.55 V. This at the same time increases the contact area between the BP and GDL, improves the contact resistance, and thus improves cell performance and mitigates the risk of local overheating. Finally, the transport of heat by the cooling liquid circulated in the channels created in between the ribs of the neighbouring BPs needs also to be considered in the design of a real stack. It prefers wider ribs.

Fig. 10. RLCDs in three cut planes located at the boundary of MEM and CL, MPL and GDL and at 3/4 of GDL on the cathode side for BPs with straight stamped channels with $CG = CP = [0.2, 1, 2]$ mm. Deviation is described in Equation (25). Minimum and maximum values of normalized local current densities are shown above the graphs.

Fig. 11. Load curves of FCs with serpentine flow-field with milled (left) and stamped (right) channels.

4.2.2. Serpentine channels

Fig. 11 summarizes load curves calculated for the second flow-field geometry studied, i.e., for FCs based on a serpentine flow-field with

milled and stamped channels. The performance of FCs with serpentine flow-fields is similar to the straight channels in the low current range. At higher current loads, however, it shows lower mass transport

polarization. As with the straight channel, FCs with wider ribs are characterized by lower performance when compared to those with narrow ribs. Voltage ranges for which a calculation was done differ due to calculation convergency.

In Fig. 12 the calculated distribution of local oxygen concentration for serpentine channels at the interface between the CL and MPL can be seen. A more detailed comparison of local oxygen concentration distribution between stamped and milled channels can be found in Figure S1, for hydrogen concentration distribution in Figure S2. In the areas under the ribs a higher concentration of oxygen is observed compared to straight channels (see Top row of Fig. 12 and Fig. 7), which leads to higher RLCDs under the ribs of the serpentine channel (see Bottom row of Fig. 12) when compared with the straight channel of the same cross-section shape of the channel (see Fig. 10). A comparison of RLCDs at different horizontal cut-planes can be seen in Figure S3. Similar velocity profiles inside the channels are observed in the straight and stamped channels (compare Fig. 9 and Figure S4), however, relatively higher velocities are observed in the areas under the inner radius. Contrary to the straight channels, convective gas transport in the GDL bulk is observed under the ribs in-between the neighbouring channels. It is driven by the pressure drop generated by the gaseous reactant flowing through the channel to the turning point and continuing in the reverse direction in the neighbouring channel. Since these two neighbouring channels are only separated by a narrow rib, the pressure difference generated by the above described way provides a sufficient driving force for the convective flow of the reactant through the GDL [40]. This effect is more pronounced in flow-fields with narrower channels (see Figure S5), because the pressure drop between the neighbouring channels is higher (see Figure S6) due to the increasing flow resistance with the decreasing channel cross-section. To some extent, this effect compensates the fact that only a small area is directly supplied with oxygen in cases with small CG (compare oxygen concentration of stamped and

milled BPs with CP = 2 mm in Fig. 12). This results in higher utilization of the areas under the ribs and more homogeneous local current density distribution (compare RLCDs of stamped and milled BPs with CP = 2 mm in Fig. 12). This is the reason for the slightly better performance of the FCs with smaller CG as seen in the load curves in Fig. 11. Areas with deficient oxygen supply are located in the corners of the FCs with CP = 1 and 2 mm. This effect is not dependent on the current loads, i.e., these areas have the lowest oxygen activity nearing zero. In these areas no catalyst is utilized and the catalyst layer or flow field design should reflect this. When comparing stamped and milled channels, the variances in performance caused by mass transport are further reduced thanks to convective gas transport between the neighbouring channels.

From these results, it can be stated that the fabrication method and, therefore, the shape of the distribution channels does not affect the performance of a FC to as high a degree as the rib and channel width parameters do. Mass transport is further improved in FCs with more complicated flow-field geometries, which introduce convective flow between neighbouring channels through the porous layer. This lessens the differences in performance between the stamped and milled channels even further. Hence, stamped BPs with optimal cross-section geometry are feasible for large-scale BP fabrication.

5. Conclusion

A 3D mathematical model was used to determine the effect of stamped and milled channel cross-section geometries in both straight and serpentine flow fields. Generally, stamped channels exhibit a slightly poorer performance than milled due to the differences in the channel cross-section. The slanted walls and the larger area with a low gas velocity in the corners of the channels have a negative effect on the transport. However, the actual performance difference between the best performing stamped and milled channels was only 2.4 %, which is

Fig. 12. **Top row:** Concentration of oxygen at the CL/MPL boundary for BPs serpentine stamped channels with CG = CP = [0.2, 1, 2] mm and milled channels with CG = 0.2 mm and CP = 2 mm at 0.65 V. Minimum and maximum oxygen concentration is shown above the graphs. Inlet is in top left corner; outlet is in bottom right corner. **Bottom row:** RLCDs at the boundary of CL and MPL at the cathode side for BPs serpentine stamped channels with CG = CP = [0.2, 1, 2] mm and milled channel with CG = 0.2 mm and CP = 2 mm. Deviation is described in Equation (25). Minimum and maximum values of normalized local current densities are shown above the graphs.

acceptable considering other benefits of the stamped bipolar plates. As it was found, the width of the ribs is a crucial parameter. In the studied cases, the observed performance differences between cases with CP = 0.2 mm and CP = 2 mm were up to twofold. Narrow ribs (CP = 0.2 mm) generally performed the best. However, for such narrow ribs, issues may arise during manufacturing. In addition, they may increase the interfacial contact resistance and cause a GDL damage. Consequently, the use of slightly wider ribs (CP = 0.4 mm) is proposed. They, despite the potential performance deterioration by of up to 8 %, are preferable from the production and real FC stack application point of view.

Straight and serpentine flow-field geometries differ from each other in the optimal channel cross-section geometry. In the case of the straight channels, the areas beneath the channels are the only areas directly supplied with reactants. It is because no gas convection between the adjacent channels. Therefore, wide channels (up to CG = 2 mm) generally perform better. However, in the case of serpentine channels, narrower channels represent a preferable option. Due to the pressure difference between the adjacent channels, they allow, beside the flow through the channels, a reactant flow through the GDL bellow the ribs. It results in an intimate contact of the reactant with the catalytic layer of the electrode. Furthermore, for the narrow ribs (i.e. CP = 0.4 mm), channel width plays a less critical role in the gas distribution. A narrower channel is then preferable due to shorter charge flow paths and thus a lower ohmic resistance. Therefore, the use of channels with channel ground widths that are 1 mm for milled and 0.2 mm for stamped channels in combination with 0.4 mm wide ribs is suggested.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Miroslav Hala: Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation. **Roman Kodým:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation. **Martin Prokop:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Martin Paidar:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Katie McCay:** Writing – review & editing. **Luca Ansaloni:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Karel Bouzek:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2024.132299>.

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